

Lentian Protects against Nonalcoholic Fatty Liver Disease by Reducing Oxidative Stress and Apoptosis via the PPAR α Pathway

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Online supplemental data

SUPPLEMENTAL TABLES

Table S1. List of antibodies.

Antibody	Company	Catalog number
AMPK α	Abclonal	A12718
p-AMPK α	Abclonal	AP0116
BCL2	Proteintech	No. 66799-1-Ig
BAX	Proteintech	No. 60267-1-Ig
Caspase3	Abclonal	A2156
cleaved-Caspase3	Abclonal	A19654
CPT1 α	Abclonal	A5307
PPAR α	Abclonal	A6697
SOD1	Abclonal	A0274
SOD2	Abclonal	A1340
NOX2	Abclonal	A19701
NOX4	Abclonal	A11274
RXR α	Abclonal	A19105

Table S2. List of primer sequences.

Gene	Sequences
Ppara-F:	5' GGCAATGGCTTTATCACACG 3'
Ppara-R:	5' TGTCATCCAGTTCTAAGGCATTG 3'
Chrebp-F:	5' CTCAACTCCATACAACCCTCG 3'
Chrebp-R:	5' CGTCGGTTCTCCATCTTGTT 3'
Srebp1-F:	5' GTTTCCGGGGAACCTTTTCCT 3
Srebp1-R:	5' TGAGCTGGAGCATGTCTTCG 3'
Cd36-F:	5' AGCAGTGATTTGACTTGTGGC 3'
Cd36-R:	5' AAGGCTAGGAAACCATCCACC 3'
Cpt1a-F:	5' GAGAATGCCAGGAGGTCATAGAG 3'
Cpt1a-R:	5' AGTCTCTGTCTCCCTCCCTCTCG 3'
Ppar γ -F:	5' ACCACTCGCATTCTTTGACA 3'
Ppar γ -R:	5' TCGCACTTTGGTATTCTTGGAG 3'
Acat-F:	5' CATCCAAGGGGTGAAGGAC 3'
Acat -R:	5' GGTGTTGCTCCTCTGCTCAT 3'
Apob-F:	5' TGCAGTCAACAGCAAGAGCA 3'
Apob -R:	5' CCTCCATCCTGAGTTGGACA 3'
Mttp-F:	5' AGAGCATCTTCCAGGGCAAA 3'
Mttp -R:	5' TATGCCCACTGGCTCGTTTT 3'
Lxr-F:	5' CAATGCCTGATGTTTCTCCTGAT 3'
Lxr -R:	5' GCTCTGCTGACTCCAACCCTAT 3'
Fxr-F:	5' ATTTACAGGCTACGGACGAGTTT 3'

<i>Fxr</i> -R:	5' GTAGAAGCCCAGGTTGGAATAGTA 3'
<i>Rxra</i> -F:	5' CACATTGGGCTTCGGGACT 3'
<i>Rxra</i> -R:	5' AGCGGTCCCCACAGATAGC 3'
<i>Sirt1</i> -F:	5' AGCGGCTTGAGGGTAATCAA 3'
<i>Sirt1</i> -R:	5' TTCGGGCCTCTCCGTATCAT 3'
<i>Gapdh</i> -F:	5' CAAAATGGTGAAGGTCGGTGTG 3'
<i>Gapdh</i> -R:	5' TGATGTTAGTGGGGTCTCGCTC 3'
<i>Tnfa</i> -F:	5' CAGGCGGTGCCTATGTCTC 3'
<i>Tnfa</i> -R:	5' CGATCACCCCGAAGTTCAGTAG 3'
<i>Il-6</i> -F:	5' TCTATACCACTTCACAAGTCGGA 3'
<i>Il-6</i> -R:	5' GAATTGCCATTGCACAACCTCTTT 3'
<i>Il-10</i> -F:	5' CAGCCGGAAGACAATAACT 3'
<i>Il-10</i> -R:	5' GCATTAAGGAGTCGGTTAGCA 3'
<i>Fas</i> -F:	5' GGAGGTGG TGATAGCCGGTAT 3'
<i>Fas</i> -R:	5' TGGGTAATCCATAGAGCCCAG 3'

SUPPLEMENTAL FIGURES

Figure S1. Flow chart of the animal experiment.

Figure S2. Effects of different concentrations of LNT treatment in PA-induced AML12. (A) TG content and (B) cell viability in AML-12 cells by PA and different concentrations of LNT treatment. Data are presented as the mean \pm SEM ($n = 3$ per group). * $p < 0.05$ compared with the control group. # $p < 0.05$ compared with the PA group.

Figure S3. Effects of LNT treatment on liver function in HFD-induced mice. (A) AST and ALT, and (B) ALP, TBIL, and BA levels in serum. Data are presented as the mean \pm SEM ($n = 8$ per group). * $p < 0.05$ compared with the control group. # $p < 0.05$ compared with the HFD group.

Figure S4. Effects of LNT treatment on inflammatory cytokines in HFD-induced mice. (A) Serum levels of TNF- α , IL-6, and IL-10 in four groups of mice. (B) Hepatic levels of TNF- α , IL-6, and IL-10. (C) Hepatic mRNA levels of TNF- α , IL-6, and IL-10 genes. Data are presented as the mean \pm SEM ($n = 8$ per group). * $p < 0.05$ compared with the control group. # $p < 0.05$ compared with the HFD group.

Figure S5. Effects of LNT treatment on related protein in PA-induced AML12 cells. Representative Western blots and quantification of (A) AMPK α p-AMPK α and (B) RXR α in AML-12 cells. Data are presented as the mean \pm SEM ($n = 3$ per group). * $p < 0.05$ compared with the control group. # $p < 0.05$ compared with the PA group.